

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_4_3_2	
Title	<i>(Quantum Geographic Information System) QGIS</i>
Category	<i>Environmental/Spatial</i>
Purpose of the method	<i>The purpose of QGIS was to visualize and produce the final Streedagh land use cover map using the resulting data from google earth engine (GEE) image analysis.</i>
Effort in time	<i>1 week</i>
Number of objects investigated	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Maram grass cover areas</i> 2. <i>Sand dunes cover areas</i> 3. <i>Other covers areas</i>
Data format	<i>Geospatial/ images</i>
Description	<i>QGIS is an open-source GIS application that enables creation, editing, analysis, visualization and publish geospatial data. In our context we input image output from GEE to produce a detailed map of the Streedagh beach land use cover after several geospatial analysis including georeferencing, removing scattered random pixels, generalization of cover classes, conversion of image to vector and cover areas calculations</i>
Basic Literature	<p>GIS Development Team. (2009). <i>QGIS Geographic Information System</i>.</p> <p>http://qgis.org Kurt Menke, G. I. S. P., Smith Jr, R., Pirelli, L., & John Van Hoesen, G. I. S. P. (2016). <i>Mastering QGIS</i>. Packt Publishing Ltd.</p> <p>Graser, A. (2016). <i>Learning Qgis</i>. Packt Publishing Ltd.</p>
Contact person within the project	<i>Fredrick Otieno</i>
Linked material	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1UDVYfPGKiVn0T9HV2VbALkgRzJVwvbUN?usp=drive_link